

Initiation of Blended Learning in the Language Learning Sects Stands More Effective and Productive among the Professional Learners: An Outline

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Abstract— Face to face teaching and learning is a traditional language learning method and there will be partial aid taken from the technical gadgets if the instructor desires to do so. This type of technology based learning is not everyone's cup of tea; the blended learning will be the best way to make teaching learning process more effective and friendly. Blended learning is an approach to English language teaching learning by introducing flexible e-learning aspects through scheduling technical, online, digital medium of learning besides traditional face to face learning. The online learning courses or subject discussions are introduced in the traditional language teaching, learning approach. This paper focuses on the preparatory analysis of the blended learning approach into language learning atmosphere; the crucial types of blended learning approaches; significant benefits that the approach can bring in learning are the major aspects discussed.

Keywords— Blended learning – Computer mediated communication (CMC) – Rotation - Flex -A La Carte – online drive.

I. INTRODUCTION

The wide range of technological developments that are leading today's teaching and learning atmospheres have been propelling the learners as well as the teachers to blend the computer -mediated communication (CMC) into the traditional face to face teaching or learning. The multifold benefits are being resulted in learning if the online elements are incorporated. The benefits such as learner engagement, enhancing the critical analysis and evidencing it in academics, promotion of social edification of knowledge as well as collaborative or two-way thinking are always possibly seen in blending online approach to face to face approach (Dehler & Parras- Hernandez, 1998; Ruberg, Moore, & Taylor 1996; Warschauer, 1997). The approach of blending or combining face to face instruction with computer mediated instruction is basically called blended learning. It has become the alternative learning approach to the traditional face to face instruction and it is adopted by more number of learners besides the educators in recent years (Graham, 2005).

II. BLENDED APPROACH

Blended approach combines the face to face learning with the computer mediated learning (Graham, 2005). Most of the researchers felt that the very acceptable reason for adopting it is that it unites best of the two major worlds, Traditional and online learning. Graham, Allen (2003) found the three major reasons for the adoption of blended learning: (1) it's a progressive pedagogy, (2) it increases the access or flexibility of acquisition of knowledge, (3) it also increases the cost efficiency. Some of the researchers have stressed that the blended learning approaches increase learning strategies to higher level; it increases peer learning besides providing the possibilities to use learner-centered strategies (Collis, Bruijstens & Veen, 2003; Morgan, 2002). In various professional development and training scenario Blended

learning is employed to cater expected outcomes among the apprentice (Lothridge, Karen: et al. 2013).

Fig. 1. Blended Learning Model.

III. CHARACTERISTICS OF BLENDED LEARNING

The learners today are highly habituated to the technology through making the smart gadgets the part and parcel of their life. Using the same for benefiting the one's learning will be a very productive initiative. Blended learning has three major characteristics that can distil by proving more effective in contrast to the traditional method of learning through face to face guidance. 1) A particular part of learning is taught with the help of digital or online media: this will help learners feel comfortable in their desired way of learning besides experiencing a change in the learning process; 2) sometimes blended learning is student-directed in terms of pace, place and time of learning, for instance there are many certificate courses offered online in which a student can register and learn on his own pace, time and comfort; 3) It provides an alluring learning experience that brings expected learning outcomes among the learners who are connected to the online learning participations. The very significant characteristic of this leaning approach is to provide flexibility in choosing time of learning, pace of learning and choice of learning.

IV. MODELS OF BLENDED APPROACH

There are some variety of blended learning models which are basically suggested by some researchers and think-tanks in the educational arena those are called Face- to- face, Rotation, Flex, self-blend, online driver.

Face To Face:

In this approach the teacher compels the required instructions and supplement with digital tools providing learning atmosphere to the learners (Dream Box 2013). Here the online learning is decided on a case-by-case basis by the teacher supplementing to the curriculum, this method also allows the students to learn topics at their own pace.

Rotation:

In this learning model the learners are given a schedule of independent online learning besides face-to-face classroom time (Kim 2014). It provides a reliable structure for the learners to learn a language, work among the other learners who have different styles of communicative competence, and practice independently in an interactive, digital atmosphere. Figure 1 shows the cycler diagram of the rotation model of blended learning approach. In this model firstly, online instructions are given to the learners; the learners work on the task as per the instructions provided; a face to face interaction is done to share varied doubts and to provide clarification or guidance to the learners; then some collaborative activities are held letting the learners collaboratively share, clarify, learn and know things rightly. Again the similar steps are scheduled situational base, lab base, individual base and classroom base.

Fig. 2. Rotation Model

Flex:

In this model most of the part of the curriculum is delivered through a digital medium and the teachers are only available to be consulted and supported to the learners face –to – face. The Flex model emphasizes on the learner’s flexibility of going for different learning modalities aiming at acquisition of their learning experiences based on their selective needs. Each student may have a customized schedule and the teacher will provide support on a flexible and needed basis. Here some learners may have substantial face-to-face support from the teacher whereas some other may have less. Figure 2 shows the flex model of blended approach in which learning is scheduled on lab, station and individual rotation basis as per the requirement of the learners as well as the teachers.

Fig. 1. Flex Model.

Self-Blend:

This model is also called ‘A La Carte’ model. This allows the learners to plan their own educational experience through choosing certain online courses which are not associated to their academic courses. The learners choose to supplement their learning through online courses. The students have to register themselves to some online courses which are not acquired from the traditional academic curriculum. This model is basically adopted by the learners who are self motivated and want to advance their chances in placements, language learning and other specific needs. NPTEL, Byzu’s, Let’s Talk, Unacademy, Grade Up, Talent sprint, English for Career etc. are some of the most popular learning channels that provide online courses to the learners as per their professional, placement and other needs.

Online Driver:

In this blended learning model students complete their entire course through online with probable teacher support and assessments. This model is quite opposite to the face-to-face model here the student works isolated way and the required materials are initially sent through online. Though the face-to-face assessment is optional, the learner can chat with the teacher for any clarification, suggestion or information. This model gives more freedom to the learners in scheduling, pacing and practice.

The choice of adopting a blended model depends on the needs of the learners and their capabilities. Blending the blended learning models together is also a good option to have lucrative outcomes in learning.

Fig. 4. The teaching and learning Cycle

The teaching and learning cycle of a blended approach is clearly shown in the figure 3. Firstly, the instructor introduces the topic for discussion among the learners face-to-face; the learners share their views or information or the reflections on the topic through online and then they share their analysis through presentations; then the teacher again introduces another topic for the next session face-to-face; the students continue their discussions over the topic through online either off class or off line; finally, learners post their discussions online, the cycle continues for the next topic. Here the learners involve in face-to-face as well as in online discussions and share their messages through a certain portal in which a threaded discussions would be done.

V. THE FACTORS INCLUDED IN BLENDED LEARNING UNITS

Five major elements are included in blended learning such as Time, Pace, Place, Path, Teacher – of- Record. The combinations of these five elements vary model to model. Some models are employed concerning time and pace whereas some on time, pace and path, and some other only time.

A. Time

The learners can learn on their flexible time and are not confined to a fixed schedule of the institution or of the instructor. Whenever the learner feel comfortable to go through the online courses or classes

B. Pace

The learners can work at their own speed, they can take more time when needed or less for certain concepts, they can also advance quickly if require

C. Place

The learners can learn by sitting inside the institution or within the campus and they also have an opportunity to work off-site, at home, outside the campus at any place other than institution.

D. Path

The learners also have possibilities of using variety of instructional approaches or models as per their requirements, the instructions such as individual instructions, small group instructions and large group instructions by using personal or online tools and techniques.

E. Teacher –of– record

Learners are guided and taught the specific course or subject by virtual instructors online and also are given support by the experts in the concern subjects to bolster online learning concepts.

VI. ADVANTAGES OF BLENDED LEARNING

In comparison to following either traditional face-to-face environment or online learning the blended learning would be acceptable for the current technically smart sections of learners. The blended learning approach has certain advantages.

- Blended approach provides flexibility at time and place for the learners in their learning and sharing practices. They

can learn concepts on their own as well as through traditional face-to-face method

- The flexibility in time and place also causes the learners to participate actively by removing their constrains
- There is a possibility to the learners to present their depth of knowledge in their own comfortable ways
- Comparing to face-to-face or purely online learning, blended learning is more effective and productive
- High levels of student achievements are possible through blended learning; it is more effective than traditional face-to-face learning
- Blended learning helps students work on their own with varied notions
- Teacher can rationalize the students' instruction to help them reach their complete potential
- Blended learning facilitates independence and collaborative learning experience to the learners
- The use of information and communication technology converts learners' attitudes towards learning
- The incorporation of information technology into class projects improves communication between teacher and students
- Blended learning reduces the expenses in the education by replacing the textbook with technical gadgets such as Smartphones, laptops and tablets.

VII. DISADVANTAGES

- Since the blended learning has flexibility in time and place, there is a chance of procrastination in the tendencies of the learners towards learning
- There is a possibility of monotonous follow up rather generation of sequential ideas and discoveries (Mikulecky L (1998))

VIII. SURVEY

A survey on the suitability and the positivity towards the incorporation of the blended approach among the varied sections of the learners was conducted. The survey was carried out through an interview held among the selected students of a reputed organization in the Rayalaseema, a region in Andhra Pradesh, India. The RGM Engineering College is one of the well known and reputed engineering colleges in the region; the students from various rural and urban areas of Andhra Pradesh province take admission into the selected institution. The researcher chose one hundred and eighty students from various streams of engineering and management for and held an interview to collect the opinions and views of acceptance towards the integration of blended approach for language learning atmosphere.

IX. INTERVIEW

The selected students of the college were interviewed and the opinions of the learners were considered. After collecting the few personal details such as 'the name', 'father's name', 'occupation of the father', 'details of born and grown up zones', 'the use of Smartphone', 'details of the constantly used apps', 'the details of the social medium that is constantly used

to connect to friends' and finally 'the opinion view on the incorporation of blended approach in language learning if it could be profitable'.

X. ANALYSIS

Out of one hundred and eighty students one hundred fifty and five students i.e. eighty six percent students have shown their agreeable response and are very positive towards the incorporation of blended approach in a language learning, out of one hundred fifty and five students one hundred and eight were the students from Engineering stream and the remaining forty seven i.e. twenty six percent were from the management; the eighteen students i.e. ten percent were on the negative and expressed their opposition towards the blended approach among these eighteen, seven were from engineering and the eleven were from management level learners; and the seven i.e. four percent of the students conveyed their intent as, they were unaware of the benefits of blended approach in language learning, these seven students were from management and, predictably, there was no student from engineering to state 'No Idea'. The table and bar graph clearly show the data analysis of the findings from the survey.

XI. OTHER RECOMMENDATIONS

TABLE 1: The attitudes of the students towards Blended Approach

Stream of the Students	Could Blended approach be profitable in language learning?					
	Yes		No		No Idea	
	The Number of Students	%	The Number of students	%	The Number of Students	%
Engineering	108	60	7	4	0	0
Management	47	26	11	6	7	4
Total	155	86	18	10	7	4

Graph 1: The attitudes of the students towards Blended Approach

The bar graph clearly shows the positivity towards the incorporation of blended approach in the language learning for the engineering and management students of the selected region. The total of eighty six percent of the students is familiar as well as believes the blended learning could be a profitable approach in the current technically smart environment. The 72% of the students who were involved in the study are the users of Smartphones, 6% of the students have no any communication gadget like mobile, tablet etc., and the remaining 22% of the students are the users of key pad mobiles. The graph 2 clearly shows the percentages of the varied types of users of the technical gadgets.

Graph 2: Use of technical gadgets by the students who participated in the survey

The high percentage of learners is the users of Smartphones through which blended learning is possible and flexible so the blended learning is the right approach to the present technically habituated professional learners.

XII. CONCLUSION

The outcome of the survey held with the undergraduate level learners of the technical and management courses clearly indicates two notable aspects; the first, most of the learners aware of blended learning in their technical spare in other words, a high number of students have the knowledge of what blended learning is and how blended learning be profitable to the current environment, the second interesting fact is that the students have made technology and social media as a part of their living today, this aspect is observed when the students have spoken out about their smart gadgets, use of the Smartphone as a obligatory medium of communication and the time they spend over sharing, commenting and liking the posts. The learners today expect flexibility, technology and less face-to-face interactions in their learning. It is apparent to incorporate blended learning in the current language learning classes.

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